

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**DENTINE HYPERSENSITIVITY AND ITS ASSOCIATED
FACTORS IN PAKISTAN**Dr Sara Ahmad¹, Dr Asma Khalid¹, Dr Ayesha Afzaal¹¹House Officer at Punjab Dental Hospital, Lahore**Article Received:** February 2020**Accepted:** March 2020**Published:** April 2020**Abstract:**

Background and objectives: Prevalence of dentine hypersensitivity (DH) may be on the increase as a result of changing lifestyles. The main objective of this study is to find the dentine hypersensitivity and its associated factors in Pakistan. **Material and methods:** This cross-sectional study was conducted in Punjab Dental Hospital, Lahore during June 2019 to January 2020. The data was collected from 200 participants. It was included those who was older than 18 years, both genders, with good general health and agreed to participate in the research. It were excluded those patients who were undergoing treatment for dental bleaching, in order to avoid overestimation of DH. **Results:** The data was collected from 200 patients of both genders. The majority of the respondents were age range 21 to 30 years and complained of symptoms of hypersensitive teeth. Of those complaining of hypersensitive teeth, males accounted for 45% (56/124) while females accounted for 55%. Statistically significant associations were found between elicited sensitivity and some socio-demographic characteristics like age, area of residence (rural or urban), and level of education ($p < 0.001$). **Conclusion:** It is concluded that dentine hypersensitivity may be on the increase and most important risk factors for dentine hypersensitivity among young.

Corresponding author:**Dr. Sara Ahmad,**

House Officer at Punjab Dental Hospital, Lahore

QR code

Please cite this article in press Sara Ahmad et al, *Dentine Hypersensitivity And Its Associated Factors In Pakistan.*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2020; 07(04).

INTRODUCTION:

Prevalence of dentine hypersensitivity (DH) may be on the increase as a result of changing lifestyles. Dentine Hypersensitivity (DH) is characterized by short sharp pain arising from exposed dentine in response to thermal, evaporative, tactile, osmotic or chemical stimuli that cannot be ascribed to any other dental defect or disease. It is an exaggerated response to a sensory stimulus that usually cause no response in a normal healthy tooth [1]. Other possible causes of pain that should be eliminated before a diagnosis of DH is made include fractured or chipped teeth, carious lesions, palatogingival grooves, leaky restorations and cracked cusps [2].

Dentinal pain is mediated by a hydrodynamic mechanism. A pain provoking stimulus applied to dentine increases the flow of dentinal tubular fluids, this mechanically activates the nerves situated at the inner ends of the tubules. The pain thus initiated is often associated with mild to severe discomfort which often affects patients' eating and drinking habits, hence affecting their quality of life. It has been reported that cold stimulus is more effective in activating intra dental nerves than do heat and probing [3]. This is supported by the observation that close to 75% of patients with DH complain of pain from cold stimuli.

The dentin hypersensitivity (DH) is defined as an acute pain of short duration due exposure of dentin, in response to stimuli typically evaporative, osmotic (chemical) and tactile, that cannot be associated with any other form of dental defect or disease [4]. The most accepted theory for DH postulates that the fluids of the exposed canaliculi are disturbed by chemical or physical changes. Those changes and movements in the intratubular fluid stimulates baroreceptors which are present in pulp and within the dentin that lead to neural discharge, resulting in painful sensation [5].

The dentin is composed by canaliculi tubules that, under normal conditions, are isolated from the external environment by enamel or cementum. For the development of DH, the dentin, along with their canaliculi, must become exposed to the oral cavity due to gingival recessions and/or loss of

enamel/cementum by erosion, abrasion, attrition abfraction, or by incorrect oral hygiene technique [6].

The main objective of this study is to find the dentine hypersensitivity and its associated factors in Pakistan.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

This cross-sectional study was conducted in Punjab Dental Hospital, Lahore during June 2019 to January 2020. The data was collected from 200 participants. It was included those who was older than 18 years, both genders, with good general health and agreed to participate in the research. It was excluded those patients who were undergoing treatment for dental bleaching, in order to avoid overestimation of DH. The tool of data collection was a web-based questionnaire that elicited information on demography, self-reported dentinal sensitivity, the trigger factor, action taken, duration of DH, and dietary pattern.

Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS Statistical Software version 17.0 (SPSS Inc., Chicago, Illinois, USA) for Windows. Frequencies and proportions were calculated. Test of significance was done with Chi square statistics. $P < 0.05$ was considered as significant.

RESULTS:

The data was collected from 200 patients of both genders. The majority of the respondents were age range 21 to 30 years and complained of symptoms of hypersensitive teeth. Of those complaining of hypersensitive teeth, males accounted for 45% (56/124) while females accounted for 55%. Statistically significant associations were found between elicited sensitivity and some socio-demographic characteristics like age, area of residence (rural or urban), and level of education ($p < 0.001$). Some oral hygiene factors such as brush frequency, brush movement, brushing after breakfast were statistically associated with elicited sensitivity. Also, elicited sensitivity was statistically associated with fresh fruit intake and fruit /vegetable juice intake ($p < 0.001$). Other life-style factors such as smoking, use of certain medications, snoring and chewing gum did not show statistical significance.

Table 01: Analysis for relationship of elicited sensitivity to oral hygiene and dietary antecedent factors

	Elicited Sensitivity		Odds Ratio (OR)	95% Confidence Limits		Chi Square X2	df	P-value
	Yes	(%)		Lower	Upper			
Total Patients	43	32.8%						
Brushing Frequency								
Once per day	30	30.5%	0.667	0.517	0.861	10.16	2	0.006*
Twice per day	10	40.9%	1.537	1.157	2.042			
Thrice per day	2	22.2%	0.582	0.120	2.815			
Brush Movement								
Various motion	14	34.7%	1.130	0.883	1.445	10.41	4	0.034*
Horizontal	11	34.4%	1.100	0.847	1.428			
Vertical	15	29.2%	0.763	0.602	0.967			
Circular	26	49.1%	2.030	1.170	3.522			
Don't know/Not sure	7	31.8%	0.954	0.386	2.356			
Brush after breakfast								
Often	10	24.9%	0.575	0.446	0.742	37.42	4	<0.001*
Occasionally	10	48.4%	2.197	1.634	2.955			
Rarely	79	32.9%	1.004	0.746	1.352			
Never	10	35.0%	1.132	0.865	1.482			
Don't know	45	29.2%	0.827	0.572	1.194			
Fresh fruits								
Often	14	36.7%	1.272	0.993	1.628	13.34	4	0.010*
Occasionally	23	31.4%	0.866	0.689	1.088			
Rarely	44	28.6%	0.798	0.551	1.155			
Never	4	17.4%	0.425	0.144	1.258			
Don't know	15	55.6%	2.611	1.212	5.627			
Fruit/Vegetable juice								
Often	13	40.9%	1.604	1.243	2.069	19.79	4	<0.001*
Occasionally	21	30.0%	0.759	0.604	0.953			
Rarely	70	29.9%	0.849	0.625	1.153			
Never	10	23.3%	0.611	0.298	1.251			
Don't know	11	55.0%	2.538	1.044	6.170			

DISCUSSION:

Globally the prevalence of dentine hypersensitivity varies from 1.34% to 74%.19-21 In the current study frequency of DH has been reported to be 36.3% which is similar to study conducted in China. Additionally, studies carried out in Nigeria and India have revealed higher rates of DH about 52.5% and 55% respectively [7]. This difference can be attributed to different methods employed for determining DH, such as using questionnaire alone or using it in combination with clinical examination, and also due to lack of patient knowledge and relating pain due to other causes with DH [8].

It has been suggested that the majority of patients demonstrated some coping mechanisms for dealing with pain as shown by the findings of the European study where peoples' perception of their pain is less than that of clinical reporting [9]. This is contrary to the findings of the current study where peoples' perception of their pain is more than that of clinical reporting. However, a sizeable percentage (27.5%) in the present study felt that the pain intensity was "very important" to their lifestyle, this should be put in proper perspective when considering the treatment need for this condition and its impact on

the quality of life. There was no differences in the prevalence of DH according to gender in the present study and the European study [10]. Similar studies have reported the same findings, while others have reported a female preponderance. This study finding corroborate the observation from the European study that the clinical elicited method of assessing DH correlate with the Schiff score for pain of DH. Also, there were significant associations between elicited sensitivity after stimulation and erosive wear which reinforced the similar findings reported in the European study [11].

CONCLUSION:

It is concluded that dentine hypersensitivity may be on the increase and most important risk factors for dentine hypersensitivity among young. Cold food was identified as risk factors for initiating sensitivity in teeth.

REFERENCES:

1. Bamise CT, Olusile AO, Oginni AO, Dosumu OO. The prevalence of dentine hypersensitivity among adult patients attending a Nigerian teaching hospital. *Oral health Prevent Dent.* 2007;5(1):49–53.
2. Chabanski MB, Gillan DG, Bulman JS, Newman HN. Clinical evaluation of cervical dentine sensitivity in a population of patients referred to a specialist periodontology department: a pilot study. *J Oral Rehabil.* 1997;24(9):666–672.
3. Rees JS, Jin LJ, Lam S, Kudanowska I, Vowles R. The prevalence of dentine hypersensitivity in a hospital clinic population in Hong Kong. *J Dent.* 2003 Sep;31(7):453–61.
4. Addy M, Mostafa P, Newcombe RG. Dentine hypersensitivity: the distribution of recession, sensitivity and plaque. *J Dent.* 1987 Dec;15(6):242–8
5. Addy M. Tooth brushing, tooth wear and dentine hypersensitivity-are they associated. *Int Dent J.* 2005;55(4 Suppl 1):261–7.
6. Gillam DG, Aris A, Bulman JS, Newman HN, Lee F. Dentine hypersensitivity in subjects recruited for clinical trials: clinical evaluation, prevalence and intra-oral distribution. *J Oral Rehabil.* 2002 Mar;29(3):226–31.
7. Dababneh R, Khouri A, Addy M. Dentine hypersensitivity - an enigma? A review of terminology, epidemiology, mechanisms, aetiology and management. *Br Dent J.* 1999 Dec 11;187(11):606–11.
8. Addy M, Hunter ML. Can tooth brushing damage your health: Effects on oral and dental tissues. *Int Dent J.* 2003;53(3):177–186.
9. Chabanski MB, Gillan DG, Bulman JS, Newman HN. Prevalence of cervical dentine sensitivity in a population of patients referred to a specialist periodontology department. *J Clin Periodont.* 1996 Nov;23(11):989–92.
10. Von Troil B, Needleman I, Sanz MA. Systematic review of prevalence of root sensitivity following periodontal therapy. *J Clin Periodontol.* 2002;(29 Suppl 3):173–7.
11. West NX, Sanz M, Lussi A, Bartlett D, Bouchard P, Bourgeois D. Prevalence of dentine hypersensitivity and study of associated factors: a European population-based cross-sectional study. *J Dent.* 2013 Oct;41(10):841–51